

Engineering and physico-chemical properties of soils of deltaic region of West Bengal. Part-II : Physico-chemical and agricultural properties of soils and attempts for correlation with engineering properties

Late Sabari Biswas^a, Surajit Ghoshal^{a,b}, S. S. Dedalal^b and S. C. Lahiri^{a,c*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Kalyani University, Kalyani-741 235, West Bengal, India

^bSoil Mechanis Section, River Research Institute, West Bengal, P.O. HRRI, Nadia, West Bengal, India

^cEmeritus Fellow, AICTE, Kalyani Govt. Engineering College, Kalyani-741 235. West Bengal, India

E-mail : sujitelahiri@yahoo.com

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Abstract : Index and engineering properties (like moisture content, liquid limit, plastic limit, plasticity etc.) of soils of deltaic region of West Bengal were studied and reported in Part-I of this paper. In Part-II of this paper, the physico-chemical properties of soils like moisture content pH, EC, exchangeable cations (K^+ , Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}) and cations under stress conditions were determined. The results were utilized to determine SAR (sodium absorption ratio), K_G (Gapon constant), PBC^K (potential buffering capacity of K) and K-status of soils. The parameters are important for the proper management of soils in agronomy.

Exchangeable Na^+ ions appears to be considerable and may affect K_G but it is not usually taken into consideration. Attempts to correlate the engineering property of soils (like particle size distribution) with concentrations of exchangeable ions are not successful.

Keywords : Correlation, cations under stress conditions, engineering properties, exchangeable cations, K_G (Gapon constant), K-status, PBC^K , physico-chemical properties, SAR (sodium absorption ratio).

Introduction

Soils are essential for the basic needs of human being and soil properties have been studied by different workers from different angles like construction purposes (houses, dams, roads etc.), agricultural purposes (agronomy and soil management), environmental and pollutional aspects¹⁻¹⁰.

It is well known that the geographical, engineering and agricultural properties of soils are to some extent dependent on their physico-chemical properties. However, little attempt was made to study the interrelationship of the different properties of soil. The problem is obviously difficult and interdisciplinary in nature but a possible correlation of the different properties may be of great help in predicting the soil properties based on interrelationship i.e. the engineering

properties of the soils based on geographical and physico-chemical properties of soils.

An attempt for the systematic investigation of the geographical, physico-chemical and agricultural properties have been made by Ghoshal *et al.*¹¹. In Part-I of the communication, we reported the physical (index and engineering) properties of soils of the deltaic region of West Bengal¹¹. We report in this communication the physico-chemical and related agricultural aspects of soils of the active deltaic region. The purpose of the work is to find out a possible correlation between the engineering and physico-chemical properties of soils and whether the soils under study are useful for agricultural purposes.

Experimental

Sample collections and transportation to the

*Present Address : Research Advisor, Central Forensic Science Laboratory, 30, Gorachand Road, Kolkata-700 014, India.

laboratory were done in a manner as described in Part-I of this paper¹¹.

The nature of the soils and their grain size were analyzed in the way given in the literature¹¹. Moisture contents of the samples were determined in the usual way by heating. Soil pH and electrical conductivity [(soil) 1 : 5 (water)] of soils were determined pH-metrically and conductometrically. To determine exchange capacity of soils, 10 g air dried soil was stirred well with 250 ml. 1 M solution of $\text{CH}_3\text{COONH}_4$ (pH 7) for 3 h in an Erlenmeyer flask in an end-to-end shaker. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was stored in polyethylene bottles. Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} were estimated by titration with EDTA. Na^+ and K^+ were determined using a flame photometer¹². Non-exchangeable K from soils was determined following the method of Pratt¹³ by resorting to one time extraction of K by boiling with 1 N HNO_3 . In this method, soil : acid (1 : 10) suspension was boiled gently for 10–15 min over a sand bath. The suspension was allowed to cool and then was filtered. Potassium extracted in this way minus the K-extracted by neutral 1 (N) NH_4OAc gave the non-exchangeable K of the soil. The other ions (Na^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+}) in the 1 N HNO_3 extracted solution were estimated titrimetrically and using flame photometer. The non-exchangeable ions were determined in the way used for the determination of non-exchangeable K as described above.

Systronic digital pH-meter (± 0.01 pH), Systronic digital conductivity bridge and Systronic digital flame photometer were utilized for the respective measurements. The results are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and discussion

Physico-chemical properties of soils from different sites are given in Tables 1 and 2. No attempt was made to determine the taxonomic characters and the proper mineralogical properties of soils. However, following the observation of Ghosh and coworker¹⁴, the soil components were considered to be mainly smectite and illite with minerals like vermiculite, kaolinite etc. in varying proportions.

Characteristic features of the soils :

Particle size determinations of the soils are reported in Part-I of this paper¹¹.

(a) Clay/silt percentages of the soils in the deltaic region were found to be high in most cases as expected and organic carbon content ranged between 0.5–1.0% (5 to 10 g/kg).

Due to dynamic nature of clay and humus content, the surface areas of the soils are fairly high. These properties are important for cation-exchange capacities of soils and exchange for ions in soil solutions. The cation-exchange capacities of soils are fairly high.

(b) Moisture content of the soils ranged between 30–50%. The air and water of soils are highly variable and their proportions are extremely important in determining suitability of soils for plant growth 20–30% air and 20–30% water usually make a good combination.

pH : pH of the soils (6.58–8.50) in general were almost neutral to alkaline (in most cases). The soils have the capacity to absorb acid rain. The soil pH influences the supply and availability of plant nutrients and toxic elements (like Fe, Mn, P, Zn, Mo etc.). Redox status of soils influences pH of the solution³. pH values of the soils are amenable for microbial growth and their activities.

Electrical conductivities of soils :

EC (dsm^{-1}) values of soil solutions (which measure the concentrations of exchangeable ions in solutions) were in the range (2.50–10.90) with exceptions. Notable exceptions were Ten-7 and Dho-1 due to less fines present in soils. The values indicated fairly high cation activities for most of the soils. It is apparent that sandy soils with low clay and humus content had very low EC values. 1 : 1 type clays with humus content and Fe and Al oxides are known to have relatively high EC values whereas 2 : 1 type clays like smectite, illite, vermiculite etc. with clay and humus content have high EC values. At neutral and slightly alkaline pH ($C_{\text{H}^+} \approx C_{\text{OH}^-} = 10^{-7}$ M), EC reflects most of the pH dependent charges of colloidal particles as well as permanent charges (due to different metal ions) as the contribution due to H^+ and OH^- towards EC are negligible⁴. The EC values indicated fairly high cation exchange capacities for most of the soils and the soils are good for agricultural purposes. To comprehend the properties of soils (normal, saline, saline-sodic etc.) and for their

classification, pH and SAR values are helpful. SAR (sodium adsorption ratio) values of the soils (Table 1) are used to characterize the sodium content of the soil solution. The relation is

$$SAR = \frac{C_{Na^+}}{(0.5[Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+}])^{0.5}} \quad (1)$$

SAR values were found to be low. The range of SAR values were 0.24–10.6.

The pH and SAR values indicated that the soils under examination usually saline soils though Dia-4, Ten-7, Kach-1 are normal soils⁴.

Rasulpur soil apparently appears to be saline-sodic though high Ca-content makes SAR < 13. Installation of drainage systems and using leaching and flushing with irrigation water with proper SAR values are some of the remedial measures for saline soils for utilization for agriculture purpose. Judicious use of gypsum is also helpful.

The cultivations of salt resistant crops like sugar beets, cotton, sorghum, barley, alfa alfa are known to be good for management of saline soils⁴.

K-status of the soils :

N, P and K are the three important elements influencing plant growth and production of which K play an important stabilizing role. K-increases crop-production and a lot of the important factors⁴ like activators of enzymes responsible for energy metabolism, starch synthesis, nitrate reduction, sugar degradation etc.

K-content of the most mineral soils are high. K is present as relatively unavailable K, slowly available K (non-exchangeable, 1–10% of total K), readily available K (exchangeable and soil solution, 1–2% of total K).

It is known that the soil solutions, K⁺ ions are in equilibrium as follows :

Potassium ion (K⁺) shifts from one another when the above equilibrium is disturbed by K-removal by crops, leaching and/or addition of K from fertilizers and crop residues. In vermiculite, smectite and other 2 : 1

minerals, K-ions are fixed but are available under stress conditions. The K-status of soils is of great practical importance as to ascertain the K-budget of soils and the application of potash fertilizer to soils for agriculture which are very much dependent on crop variety. Loss of K from soils due to leaching, crop removal and luxury consumption of K must be known to have a proper K-budget even if the concentrations of non-exchangeable and exchangeable K of soils are known.

Distribution of potassium in soils is dependent on two fundamental processes viz. fixation and release. Clay mineral, the nature of soil colloids, addition of potassium fertilizers, soil reactions, wetting and drying of organic matter, complimentary cations and presence of excess lime are some other factors affecting K-fixation in soils. The release of K is governed by the composition and concentration of K in soil solution and the mineralogical composition of soil clays.

Different aspects of soil properties like K-utilization of soil by plants, K-uptake and release of non-exchangeable K were studied extensively^{15–32}. The K-status and K-buffering power of the soil are two important contributing factors affecting K-desorption in soil solution. These are dependent on soil texture, type of clay and minerals present.

Beckett^{24,25} applied the concept of quantity (*Q*) and intensity (*I*) to the mineral nutrient status of soils. The intensity factor (*I*) is a measure of readily available (to the root) K in the soil solution and the quantity factor (*Q*) is a measure of the soil to maintain the level of K in the soil solution over the period of time the crop is being produced. This is related to exchangeable and to some extent due to non-exchangeable K of the soil. However, *Q* factor designates the K sources capable of helping to replenish the soil solution (intensity) level of K. These require the study of solution exchange phase interactions involving K⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺ ions²³.

The potential buffering capacity of soil K (PBC^K) indicates the ability of soil to maintain the intensity (*I*) or availability of K⁺ ion in the soil solutions which varies with the amount of labile K (quantity *Q*) and is useful in explaining K-supplying power of soils. Forms of K and *Q/I* parameters were studied extensively for better understanding of K⁺ release into the soil solution and consequent uptake by plants^{10,24–32}.

Table 1. Physico-chemical properties of soils of deltaic region of West Bengal

Sample	Place/ District	Geogra- phical region	Soil charac- ter	Fines content (%)	Moisture content (%)	pH	EC (dsm ⁻¹)	Organic carbon (%)	Exchange- able Ca ⁺⁺ [C mole (P ⁺), kg ⁻¹]	Exchange- able Mg ⁺⁺ [C mole (P ⁺), kg ⁻¹]	Exchange- able Na ⁺ [C mole (P ⁺), kg ⁻¹]	Exchange- able K ⁺ [mol (P ⁺) kg ⁻¹]	SAR [C mole, kg ⁻¹]	K [mole, kg ⁻¹]
Jag-1	Jagatpur 24-Prgs (N)	6-7	Entisols	H	49.9	8.50	3.10	0.65	24.49	6.68	0.95	0.61	0.24	1.46
Bas-1	Basanti 24-Prgs (S)	7	Entisols	H	33.0	8.40	8.46	0.40	33.92	4.71	8.69	1.96	1.98	1.17
Jhar-1	Jharkhali 24-Prgs (S)	7	Entisols	H	37.3	8.30	10.40	0.50	13.20	5.12	14.56	1.66	4.81	1.66
Dho-1	Dhosa 24-Prgs (S)	6-7	Entisols	L	30.6	8.10	1.70	0.35	31.25	3.68	10.86	1.32	2.60	1.38
Dia-1	Diamond Harbour 24-Prgs (S)	6	Entisols	H	37.3	8.10	3.15	0.45	3.78	1.88	17.50	2.15	10.40	3.42
Dia-4	Do	6	Entisols	H	39.6	7.18	2.52	0.30	16.80	18.95	19.56	2.10	4.63	1.39
Ten-1	Tentulia 24-Prgs (S)	6-7	Entisols	H	31.9	7.90	5.90	0.38	5.32	8.17	21.74	0.64	8.37	2.08
Ten-7	Do	Do	Entisols	L	25.5	6.95	0.57	0.29	6.59	4.71	6.74	1.56	2.83	2.71
Raj-1	Rajnagar 24-Prgs (S)	7	Entisols	H	30.0	8.00	9.50	0.36	9.50	20.43	7.50	1.05	1.94	1.31
Shi-1	Shibpur 24-Prgs (S)	7	Entisols	H	37.0	8.50	10.90	0.53	26.30	4.83	18.04	1.92	4.57	1.26
Kach-1	Kachuberia, Sagar 24-Prgs (S)	7	Entisols	H	45.8	8.30	10.00	0.45	10.00	23.40	13.25	1.74	3.24	1.23
Dig-1	Digha-I Medinipur (E)	8	Entisols	N	32.5	6.58	3.00	-	-	-	10.00	0.46	-	-
Gob-1	Patharpratima 24-Prgs (S)	7	Entisols	H	50.8	8.20	7.92	1.05	5.02	1.78	19.50	2.10	10.57	2.82
Kak-1	Kakdeep 24-Prgs (S)	7	Entisols	M	29.5	8.15	9.50	0.83	10.80	21.0	12.19	1.89	3.06	1.27
Rasul-1	Rasulpur Medinipur (E)	8	Entisols	M	35.0	6.70	9.00	0.39	24.00	15.82	26.09	0.60	5.85	1.15

Table 2. Concentrations of exchangeable ions under stress condition (HINO₃ treatment)
(All concentrations are in C mole (F⁺), kg⁻¹ of dry soil)

Sample	Place/ District	Geogra- phical region	Soil character	Moisture content (%)	Total K ⁺	Exch K ⁺	Non- Exch K ⁺	Total Na ⁺	Exch Na ⁺	Non- Exch Na ⁺	Total Ca ²⁺	Exch Ca ²⁺	Non- Exch Ca ²⁺	Total Mg ²⁺	Exch Mg ²⁺	Non- Exch Mg ²⁺
Bas-1	Basanti 24-Prgs (S)	7	Silty clay (entisols)	33.0	6.26	1.96	4.30	10.65	8.69	1.96	34.00	33.92	0.08	24.01	4.71	19.3
Jag-1	Jagatpur 24-Prgs (S)	6-7	Sandy silt (entisols)	49.9	2.35	0.61	1.47	4.56	0.95	3.61	-	24.49	-	-	6.68	-
Jhar-1	Jharkhali 24-Prgs (S)	7	Entisols	37.3	8.30	10.40	0.50	13.20	5.12	14.56	1.66	4.81	1.66	-	-	-
Dho-1	Dhosa 24-Prgs (S)	6-7	Entisols	30.6	8.10	1.70	0.35	31.25	3.68	10.86	1.32	2.60	1.38	-	-	-
Dia-1	Diamond Harbour 24-Prgs (S)	6	Entisols	37.3	8.10	3.15	0.45	3.78	1.88	17.50	2.15	10.40	3.42	-	-	-
Dia-4	Do	6	Entisols	39.6	7.18	2.52	0.30	16.80	18.95	19.56	2.10	4.63	1.39	-	-	-
Ten-1	Tentulia 24-Prgs (S)	6-7	Entisols	31.9	7.90	5.90	0.38	5.32	8.17	21.74	0.64	8.37	2.08	-	-	-
Ten-7	Do	Do	Entisols	25.5	6.95	0.57	0.29	6.59	4.71	6.74	1.56	2.83	2.71	-	-	-
Raj-1	Rajnagar 24-Prgs (S)	7	Entisols	30.0	8.00	9.50	0.36	9.50	20.43	7.50	1.05	1.94	1.31	-	-	-
Shi-1	Shibpur 24-Prgs (S)	7	Entisols	37.0	8.50	10.90	0.53	26.30	4.83	18.04	1.92	4.57	1.26	-	-	-
Kach-1	Kachuberia, Sagar 24-Prgs (S)	7	Entisols	45.8	8.30	10.00	0.45	10.00	23.40	13.25	1.74	3.24	1.23	-	-	-

From the Q/I plot, several parameters may be obtained to characterize the K^+ status, release dynamics of soil K^+ , namely, the equilibrium activity ratio for K^+ (AR_e^K), linear potential buffering capacity for K^+ (PBC^K) and specifically fixed K^+ (K_x)^{23,31-33}.

For the K -($Ca + Mg$) interactions^{26,27}, the Gapon equation leads to the relation

$$K_G = \frac{\text{Exch } K^+}{\text{Exch } (Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+})} \times \frac{(a_{Ca^{2+}} + a_{Mg^{2+}})^{1/2}}{a_{K^+}} \quad (2)$$

K_G is the Gapon cation-exchange selectivity coefficient, Exch is the exchangeable cations in mol (P^+) kg^{-1} and a is the activity of the cations. Obviously, K_G cannot be a true thermodynamic constant but has been assumed to have an indistinguishable thermodynamic value for ranges of monovalent ion exchange phase loadings encountered in agricultural soil systems^{26,27}. Rearrangement of above equation gives

$$(\text{Exch } K^+) = (\text{Exch } Ca^{2+} + \text{Exch } Mg^{2+}) K_G \cdot a_{K^+} / (a_{Ca^{2+}} + a_{Mg^{2+}})^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{or } (\text{Exch } K^+) = (\text{Exch } Ca^{2+} + \text{Exch } Mg^{2+}) K_G \cdot AR^K \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } AR^K = \frac{a_{K^+}}{a^{1/2}_{(Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+})}} = \frac{C_{K^+}}{C^{1/2}_{(Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+})}} \times \frac{Y_{K^+}}{Y^{1/2}_{(Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+})}} \quad (5)$$

where C is the molar concentration of the respective ion and Y is the activity coefficient which can be calculated using Davies equation³⁴,

$$\log Y = -0.509 Z_1^2 \mu^{1/2} / (1 + \mu^{1/2}) + 0.2 \mu \quad (6)$$

Z_1 = valency of the ion, μ is the ionic strength and is roughly equal to

$$\mu = 0.0127 EC^{35}. \quad (7)$$

This leads to

$$\frac{d(\text{Exch } K^+)}{dAR^K} = PBC^K = (\text{Exch } Ca^{2+} + \text{Exch } Mg^{2+}) K_G \quad (8)$$

For most agricultural soils under K -fertilization, the

contribution of Exch K^+ to the CEC is insignificant i.e. $\text{Exch } (Ca^{2+} + Mg^{2+}) \gg \text{Exch } K^+$ so that equation may be approximated as

$$PBC^K = CEC \cdot K_G^{23} \quad (9)$$

where CEC refers to the cation exchange capacity of soils.

To determine the release pattern of reserve potassium from the soils, many of the workers determined the non-exchangeable K from soils following the method of Pratt¹² by resorting to one time extraction with boiling 1 (M) HNO_3 . They also determined step K by successive extractions with 1 (M) HNO_3 and constant rate K (CR- K)²⁸⁻³⁰ as described by Haylock³⁶ and modified by Maclean³⁷. The threshold values of K -release in the soils were obtained following the method of Datta and Sastry³⁸.

In the present work K -status (exchangeable and non-exchangeable) of soils from a large number samples from the alluvial region of South Bengal were determined. But step- K , CR- K etc. were not determined. The values of the exchangeable K and non-exchangeable K together with other exchangeable ions are reported in Table 2. The Gapon-selectivity constants from K - Ca exchange (a measure of relative tenacity of K with which it is held in planar sites and the wedge zone of clay) of the soils are also presented in Table 1. The soil properties of the samples were different but attempt to correlate the exchangeable K and the Gapon constant K_G was not successful.

It is to be noted though unavailable K (stress K) can be obtained by digestion of soils by nitric acid, but all the unavailable K can be utilized by plants may not be a reality as the conditions similar to digestion of soils with nitric acid (particularly for step k and rate constant K) can be hardly be considered practicable.

K_G is not an ideal thermodynamic constant but can be regarded to be ideal for soil solutions and is dependent not only on exchangeable K but also on other exchangeable ions and their activity coefficient. It is to be noted that Na^+ ion has been found to take the place of K^+ in nutrition of certain plants. Excess Na (concentrations are fairly high), however, has the capability of disturbing the other exchangeable ions present in the soils system and disturb the equilibrium affecting K_G values.

The greater the K_G the greater will be potential buffering capacity (PBC^K) of the soil solution system. Addition of lime will affect K_G . Similarly, the addition of potash fertilizer will increase the concentration of soluble K and non-exchangeable K will not be disturbed but excess K will definitely disturb the equilibrium.

Stress K is a rough estimate of the available K under stress. Recommendation for the addition of K fertilizer should take into the consideration the availability of non-exchangeable K but at the same time K-loss due to leaching must be considered though no quantitative estimate of K-loss due to leaching is possible. It is known that the Ganga water contains appreciable amount of K and sediments contain appreciable reserve of K though there is sufficient K-loss by leaching^{7,8,39}.

It is interesting to note that in most cases, exchangeable Na^+ and Mg^{2+} ions were greater than those of K^+ and Ca^{2+} but the reverse was true for ions under stress conditions. Moreover, in calculating K^+ ions, contributions due to Na^+ ions were neglected though they were present in appreciable amounts.

A correlation between the concentrations of exchangeable ions with the engineering properties particularly with the particle size¹¹ distribution of soils were attempted without much success but the permeability of soils were usually low. EC (related to exchange capacity) and exchangeable K are to some extent dependent on clay % and silt % respectively. Clay contents are also related to high expansibility and low permeability. These are also related to Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} salts but the data are small to have positive correlation¹⁹. The soils, in general, are more useful for agricultural purposes but soil conditioning may be necessary in some cases. For better comprehension of the engineering and geographical properties of soils, detailed mineralogical investigations of the soils including complete analysis of the constituents like Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , H^+ etc. (total ion concentrations rather than the exchangeable ions) and Fe, Al and Ca silicates, phosphates are necessary. We are unable to undertake such studies. But Na_2SiO_3 and lime treatment may be useful for construction purposes¹⁰. The engineering structures should be founded on the sub-structures capable of distributing load through the existing sub-soils (normally consolidated clays).

More work in this direction is in progress.

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